

Agrobiodiversity Extensive Case: Systems Map, Leverage Points, Narrative of Change, Indicators, Monitoring and Broader Impacts

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PLANET4B

BETTER DECISIONS FOR BIODIVERSITY AND PEOPLE

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Introduction

The cases within PLANET4B are supposed to create a systems map with their stakeholder boards to visualise the system investigated by the case. In our case, it is the **system of open-pollinated vegetable seeds**, within the broader system of agrobiodiversity. The systems map is evidently a simplified picture of any actual systems but, at the same time, it contains the most important components and the primary relationships among them. Our systems map can be found in Chapter 1.

We also prepared an analysis in order to distinguish the leverage points of the system under study. To do this, we analysed the expert interviews we conducted through the lens of the leverage point (LP) framework by Donella Meadows. This analysis can be found in Chapter 2.

Linked to the systems map and the LP analysis another task of ours was to choose an intervention that pushes the system at a specific leverage point which causes a series of further changes in the system that eventually lead to the transformation of the system itself. This transformation aims to create a system that supports biodiversity more than the current one – the diversity of open-pollinated vegetables in our case. The narrative of the intervention and the broader impacts it creates (i.e., impacts beyond the system under study) can be found in Chapter 3.

The present report was prepared by the two ESSRG researchers (Borbála Lipka and György Pataki) who lead the P4B agrobiodiversity extensive case but was extensively discussed with the Agrobiodiversity Stakeholder Board. The process of preparing this report was the following: the two ESSRG researchers conducted 20 expert interviews (incl. members of the Agrobiodiversity Stakeholder Board), applied the LP framework to analyse the interview texts, produced an interim report on the agrobiodiversity systems map, the LP analysis and the narrative of change that was discussed by the Agrobiodiversity Stakeholder Board during an online board meeting (24-06-2024) that resulted in the refinement of the report; then the two ESSRG researchers prepared a report on indicators, monitoring strategy and broader impacts which were extensively discussed by the Agrobiodiversity Stakeholder Board during an online board meeting (31-10-2024) that resulted in a refinement and finalisation of this report.

1 Systems map

In PLANET4B, we used the visual tool of the so-called onion diagram (see Leventon et al. 2024) to outline the systems map. This is one of the easiest visualisation techniques that presents sub-systems embedded in each other. The onion metaphor allows us to present different layers of the system and to expect that the different components and the connections between them will reveal themselves. It's important to note that the onion diagram gives a static picture about the system, however, all the systems, including seed systems are dynamic and in constant change. These dynamics cannot be interpreted from the picture but to understand the whole context, we have to consider the ever-changing dynamics of actors and factors. Our systems map is summed up on the following picture:

There are two layers on the onion diagram of the system of open-pollinated vegetable seeds. In the inner circle we showed the actors and factors that directly affect the system. These actors and factors form the main dynamics of the system. The position, power and relationships of the actors as well as the opportunities and limits created by the institutional factors run the system.

We see the *on-farm* conservationists as one of the main actor groups. They are the amateur or hobby gardeners who experiment with different varieties, save their own seeds, and manage more or fewer varieties in their own gardens. Typically, they conserve a variety throughout generations, they swap seeds in their neighbourhoods and many times they're conscious enough to take the conservation of a variety seriously. The other „extreme” of *on-farm* conservationists are the market gardeners (market gardens) that are typically active in alternative food networks. They operate community supported agriculture systems, farm ecologically and many of them are open and committed towards the principles of permaculture.

On the scale between amateur and market gardeners, we find subsistence farmers and gardeners who do conservation activities in their own garden or their own farm. Because their living depends on it, their conservation activities are usually more planned and are on a bigger scale than hobby gardeners but they not necessarily plan with selling on the market. Some subsistence farmers also have a contract with the Hungarian national gene bank (Hungarian abbrev.: NBGK) and are a part of a country-wide *on-farm* conservation network.

Consumers of the vegetables grown by market gardeners (SSC consumers) are important actors of the demand side. Short supply chains (SSCs) offer a viable alternative for retail food systems based on global supply. And though some landrace varieties can make it to shelves of supermarkets or food retailers as plantings or crops, the higher interest from consumers, the higher commitment towards open-pollinated or local varieties and landraces is more characteristic to SSCs.

The decisions of seed producers and seed distributors obviously directly affect the conservation of open pollinated varieties and agrobiodiversity. These actors have a close connection to market gardeners whose growing systems allow only limited experimentation with varieties, or do not allow this kind of activity at all. These farmers have to provide food for their consumers, have to reliably bring a consistent quantity and quality of crops, therefore the pressure of efficiency and productivity limits how many and what kind of varieties they can try out. They need tested varieties that have already proven to be productive. Seed producers and seed distributors can support them in providing this kind of varieties.

Another important actor can be a main decision maker of the catering industry: the chef. One source of income for farmers involved in *on-farm* conservation can be supplying restaurants that are looking for seasonal and exotic vegetables, like to experiment and where consumers also accept and seek this kind of experience.

Considering state actors, the Hungarian national gene bank (in Hungarian: Nemzeti Biodiverzitás- és Génmegőrzési Központ, NBGK) has a crucial role, not only by preserving the genetic diversity and the physical seeds of varieties but also by

distributing these seeds. This happens, on one hand, within the *on-farm* conservation network with contracted gardeners, and by providing opportunity to anybody, including hobby gardeners, an opportunity for experimenting with varieties and *in-situ* conservation on the other. Another important state actor that has a direct effect on the dynamics of the system is the controlling body of the seed system. Its expectations about open-pollinated varieties can directly motivate or deter farmers when considering whether to use a specific variety (or a variety coming from a specific source) or not.

When we talk about agrobiodiversity, we obviously cannot overlook the non-human peers of the system. Seeds are just as important actors of the system as humans. Seeds embody the essence of life, they fascinate many of us. Seeds create connections: they embody our connection to the circle of life as well as the connection to each other. They are the main characters of seed swaps. Seeds fulfill the life that lies in them together with their living and lifeless environment.

In the outer circle of the systems map we see the actors and institutional factors that have an indirect effect on system dynamics. They're interconnected, affect each other while they also influence the actors, factors and their connections in the inner circle.

Typically, European and Hungarian land use legislation, subsidy policies and control system, land policy, tax system and the agricultural and rural policies of all-time governments are factors that empower or limit the opportunities of any agrobiodiversity system.

It's also important to mention the public health, education and science sectors. Dietetics, eating habits, agri- and horticultural courses and the financing of research are all important components of a broader context. They have a significant effect on the habits of consumers, the knowledge of farmers and gardeners, the activities of creating and distributing knowledge.

Consumer habits, values, gastro-culture, markets and retail market chains generally can influence the dynamics of the system. The organisation of public catering can be a particularly big demand factor but it also influences consumer expectations. Generally speaking, the current market-based society and the paradigm of modernity seriously limit the initiatives trying to empower diversity by institutionalising our societies and food supply chains along the principles of growth, productivity and efficiency. When saying 'market-based society' we refer to the analysis of Károly Polányi that he explains in his book *The Great Transformation*. We do not simply refer to market economy but that the institutional logic of market exchange does not only define the operation of the economic system but also other systems and sectors and in the end commercialises and commodifies the whole society. When talking about 'the paradigm of modernity' we mean the culturally embedded approach where humans want to control and dominate the systems of economy, society and nature. Here we can see the interconnection of the trio of 'big business–big science–big government' where usually even the 'greening' attempts are big-scale, based on scientific and technological, bureaucratic solutions that require large investments and consider growth and return as a base line. This is completely up against the paradigm of 'small is beautiful' that became popular thanks to the work of Ernst Schumacher, an early ecological economist.

2 Leverage Points

The conception of leverage points (LPs) has an important role in the frameworks of system analysts working with complex systems (Abson et al. 2017). LPs are points of a system where a smaller change can trigger spill-over effects that can lead to the transformation of the system.

2.1 The leverage point framework according to Meadows

Within PLANET4B we follow the analytic scheme that was explained by Donella Meadows, originally defining nine main leverage points (Meadows 1999). These leverage points are the following, going from the 'shallow' towards 'deep' leverage points:

9. Parameters
8. Material flows and nodes of material intersection
7. Regulating negative feedback loops
6. Driving positive feedback loops
5. Information flows
4. The rules of the system (incentives, punishments, constraints)
3. The distribution of power and the rules of the system
2. The goals of the system
1. The paradigm out of which the system arises

Later the original nine LPs became twelve by the separation of 'Material flows and nodes of material intersection' into 'The sizes of buffers and other stabilising stocks, relative to their flows' and 'The structure of material stocks and flows'. Also, two new LPs appeared: bringing in the role of time 'the lengths of delays, relative to the rate of system change' and 'the ability to transcend paradigms'. Within PLANET4B, we apply this extended framework with 12 LPs (see Leventon et al. 2021 and 2024).

2.2 The application of leverage point framework to the system of agrobiodiversity

We created the LP analysis of the system of agrobiodiversity based on the expert interviews. Our methodology was using the 12 LPs as a code to 'encode' the texts of the interviews according to which LP is connected to the different parts of the interview. The following chart sums up our analysis:

Leverage points	Agrobiodiversity leverage points – Analysis based on the expert interviews
12. Parameters (subsidies, taxes, standards)	Financial support for <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • establishing small / family farms • small-scale arable farming, greening • organic farmers (so they do not have to ask for so high prices) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 'research farmers' who take part in research projects

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> growing the number of varieties adaptable to organic farming
11. The sizes of buffers and other stabilising stocks, relative to their flows	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> conservation / development of the genetic diversity of cultivated plants
10. The structure of material stocks and flows	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> providing the availability to the seeds of open-pollinated varieties providing infrastructure for small-scale seed growing
9. The length of delays relative to the rate of system change	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> easier registration process for open-pollinated varieties
8. The strength of negative feedback loops, relative to the impacts they are trying to correct against	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Subsidies/ obligation for water retention Correcting bad water management practices regenerative soil management should be a part of organic farming officially strict regulation of GMO and NGT labelling
7. The gain around driving positive feedback loops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cooperation of gardeners/farmers in order to save seeds (e.g. coordinated seed saving) reduction of meat consumption and the amount of food waste less subsidies for conventional farming (especially restructuring the areas-based subsidies)
6. The structure of information flows (who does and does not have access to what kind of information)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Access to knowledge, know-how (seed saving, cultivation Technologies, processing) Education (farmers, consumers, decision makers, children, students) 'farmer researchers ' have to be involved in the planning and evaluation of participatory research projects
5. The rules of the system (incentives, constraints, punishments)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Less administration if someone wants to grow diverse varieties for sale restructuring agricultural subsidies (see LP12 and LP7) promoting and supporting local solutions against those offered by multinational companies including agrobiodiversity as a topic to agricultural university curricula (should be taught outside of the context of organic farming too) professional forum where local stakeholders can be present or send a representative financing research projects that are able to analyse agrobiodiversity as a complex system fair use should be an aspect of breeding (e.g. opportunity for seed saving, no patents) fair and transparent legislation for small-scale and individual seed growers it should be easier to grow landraces and local varieties for sale resistant/open-pollinated varieties should be easier to Administrate creation of a forward-thinking strategy for growing plant reproductive materials promoting and financing participatory research projects bigger appreciation and involvement (in planning, evaluation, finances) for the participating farmers in agricultural research projects

4. The power to add, change or self-organise system structure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Professional forum among stakeholders in order to improve communication and build mutual trust • supporting communities and spaces that are connected to seeds (e.g. community seed banks, gardening clubs) • Disseminating good practices • country-wide seed network (with individual and community seed banks) • bringing back and spreading landraces at their lands of origin <hr/> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • cooperation among different stakeholders (e.g. national gene banks, community seed banks, breeders, CSAs, farmers) • creating a network of small-scale seed growing companies • moneyfree economy in local communities • camps (for children), workshops (for adults) • promoting participatory projects (e.g. on-farm variety testing, Breeding, seed CSAs) • on-farm network for the gene bank in order to multiply the seeds of landraces • courses about agrobiodiversity and seed saving for gardeners, CSAs, market gardeners
3. Goals of the system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating SSCs • enhancing the demand for diversity (e.g. in restaurants, public catering) • the goal of agriculture: healthy, affordable, culturally relevant food for all
2. The paradigm out of which the system arises	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • openness • experimental attitude • agroecology • permaculture • systems thinking • looking for connections, similarities, recognising the strength In diversity • non-violent communication
1. The ability to transcend paradigms	-

As a next step, we chose one LP that we found particularly important in order to transform the system of agrobiodiversity (in Hungary). At this LP, there are already some initiatives going on, therefore it seems to be reasonable to think over how we can help to transform the system in order to support agrobiodiversity better. In the next chapter we aimed to create a plain narrative about the dynamics of change. It's important to note that the LP framework by itself may appear too rigid and unable to

show the connections, dynamics. The narrative below aims to correct this rigidity, to reveal the opportunity of dynamic use of the LP framework.

3 The Narrative of the Intervention

Many of our interviewees emphasised that the key to successful conservation and management of agrobiodiversity is locality: the conservation of the diversity of vegetables is in the hands of the smallest actors who are usually considered „amateurs” - hobby gardeners, small-scale farmers, subsistence farmers, „seed-lunatics”. The market logic of modern agrobiodiversity and seed production is inevitably swinging commercial seed production towards mechanisation, thinking big and thus, the need for uniformity. A direction that returned in many interviews is the promotion and support of local initiatives and participatory research projects as well as disseminating good practices. As an example, we chose an intervention that has already appeared in Hungary, in the form of a network of hubs organised by Magház Association. We think that this network embodies the ideal system of open-pollinated vegetable seeds that our interviewees explained. In the next thought experiment, we examine the broader impacts of supporting and developing this already existent network.

Intervention: building / supporting the formulation of a national network based on local (regional) seed(bank) hubs (LP4)

The intervention we chose as an example falls into LP4 (the power to add, change or self-organise a system structure) thus helps to transform the system structure and belongs to the category of deep LPs that have a higher potential to transform the system on the long term. Instead of a centralised, bureaucratic seed system, a seed network based on hubs adaptive to local demands and environments is more resilient and allows quicker adaptation to the rapidly changing or even unpredictable climate. A network like this does not come into existence as a result of a central will or organisation; it is created by the interconnection of grassroots movements, first spontaneously, then in a more conscious way. Eliminating the heterogeneity, the diversity of the network is not one of the goals. The strength of the network lies

precisely in the fact that many different actors, with many different organisational solutions work, cooperate and learn from each other. What holds them together is a shared vision of agriculture and food production, and a love and respect for seeds and plants. It may also be simply the joy of doing things together that drives many as their awareness grows. The speed and dynamics of intervention can not be controlled by anyone. Ideology (resistance, creation of something new, etc.) may also become secondary to action, but diversity may remain a feature in this way as well.

Impact

The most visible effect of a decentralised system like this is the change in the flow of information (LP6) as there is a lot of space for exchanging knowledge and experiences as well as making contacts among local gardeners and farmers. Supporting or creating local centers also creates opportunities to take advantage of already existing contacts, for example cooperating or organising events with local institutions (libraries, community centres, etc.). This way locals who are not gardening or farming but are interested in the theory and practice of sustainability also have an opportunity to join. Exchanging experiences and knowledge empowers the idea that all knowledge is valuable, everybody has some experiences that can be useful or interesting for others.

The change in the flow of information and the opportunity to contact other like-minded locals also creates new possibilities for local gardeners and farmers to start new cooperations or programmes connected to agrobiodiversity. Some of the programs can be open days on farms/in gardens, showing best practices, tasting events, local seed saving courses, etc. There's even the possibility of coordinated seed saving where the farmers or gardeners decide among themselves who save the seeds of which variety and then share the seeds with each other (solidary economy based on mutual exchange). Getting seeds is not limited to commercial varieties, it becomes possible to share the seeds of local varieties, saved by local residents. This transformation creates new dynamics in the processes of the system, that helps to strengthen diversity in the end. Local collaborations lead to new contacts that may result in new initiatives, cooperations thus creating a constant possibility of new social connections, community events, economic opportunities (the gain around driving positive feedback loops, LP7).

New ways of information flow also start transforming the material part of the system as experimenting with diverse varieties and saving seeds (that can later be exchanged) becomes more important. Acquiring seeds is not limited to commercial varieties any more, personal seed exchanges and organised seed swaps appear, thus there's a change in the structural flows and stocks of materials (seeds, in this particular case) (LP10). Better availability of locally adapted seeds and the higher number of local residents engaged in agrobiodiversity management results in a growth in the number of species and varieties grown around the regional centres (this equals to the size of buffers in LP11 as the genetic diversity of cultivated plants is what enhances the possibility of adaptation to local demands and environments).

In the end, the changed system structure, the new system processes and material flows contribute to transformations on the highest level: the recreation of the goals of the system. Instead of focusing on the productivity of commercial seed production, the importance of resilience comes to the forefront, the emphasis moves from constant growth to the connection of different actors, the strength that lies within diversity (of species and varieties). The growth paradigm of market-based society is exchanged by the paradigm of care (LP2), at least partially; the importance of connections and the quality (of crops) becomes recognised. This also brings the definition of new goals for the system such as producing good quality, affordable and culturally appropriate food for everyone instead of producing as much cheap food as possible (LP3).

The change of paradigm further strengthens local cooperations for the conservation of agrobiodiversity (LP7) and thus the growth of the genetic diversity of cultivated plants (LP11) and the nature of the goals of the system (LP3).

4. Monitoring indicators

We created a narrative of change about the system of agrobiodiversity (the seeds of open-pollinated vegetables) based on the leverage point analysis. In this chapter, our task is to propose indicators to this narrative of change that can characterise or measure the change with either quantitative or qualitative indicators. We also have to think about what kind of data are needed and what actors need to take action so that the evaluation/measurement of change is strategically thought over. This latter will be the monitoring strategy of indicators.

To achieve these goals we broke up the narrative of change into „desired changes” and assigned qualitative or quantitative indicators to them. We marked the goal of each indicator or indicator group and the obstacles that might prevent the successful use of each indicator or indicator group.

Desired change 1: Establishment of a network of (regional) seed hubs

Purpose: monitoring the status and development of the network (Which hubs are more or less active? Which hubs need support? Etc.)

Indicator 1.1: Number of hubs

Indicator 1.2: Number of active hubs

Indicator 1.3: Intensity of connections between hubs

Indicator 1.4: Who participates at the events of the hub

Indicator 1.5: Number of varieties preserved by the hub

Indicator 1.6: Number of varieties cultivated per year by the hub

Indicator 1.7: Number of gardens or gardeners included in the hub's activities

Indicator 1.8: Number of events per year organised by the hub

Indicator 1.9: Number of hubs engaged in advocacy

Indicator 1.10: Intensity of awareness raising activity

Data collection methods:

- independent researcher collects data (interviews, questionnaires, every 3 years)
- own statistics and reports by the hubs (annually)

Obstacles to indicator validity:

- validity of the indicators is heavily influenced by the quality of data and it can be an obstacle that the hubs don't have enough resources to prepare their own statistics and reports;
- financing of independent researchers and research programs is uncertain which threatens the implementation of monitoring activities;
- the ambiguity of terms (e.g. what does „active” mean?) can lead to uncertain and unreliable data;
- „the myth of numbers”: dominance of quantification over quality and meaning.

Desired change 2: Decentralised information flow

Purpose: better understanding of knowledge needs, gaps, and the development of information and knowledge exchange.

Indicator 2.1: Number of online content on agrobiodiversity

Indicator 2.2: Number of joint events among the hubs

Indicator 2.3: Number of new contacts established

Indicator 2.4: Number of local community institutions engaged

Indicator 2.5: Report of the events

Indicator 2.6: Number of new collaborations started

Indicator 2.7: Number of trainings on agrobiodiversity

Indicator 2.8: Number of actors engaged in awareness raising, advocacy and policy making

Indicator 2.9: Increase in the number of online followers of agrobiodiversity organisations

Data collection methods:

- independent researcher collects data (interviews, questionnaires, online content analysis every 3 years)
- own statistics and reports by the hubs (annually)
- quick questionnaires on the main events among participants

Obstacles to indicator validity:

- validity of the indicators is heavily influenced by the quality of data and it can be an obstacle that the hubs do not have enough resources to prepare their own statistics and reports;
- financing of independent researchers and research programs is uncertain which threatens the implementation of monitoring activities;
- the ambiguity of terms (e.g. what does „active” mean?) can lead to uncertain and unreliable data;
- „the myth of numbers”: dominance of quantification over quality and meaning.

Desired change 3: Positive feedback loops as new dynamics in the system

Purpose: Better understanding the development of the dynamics of the system.

Indicator 3.1: Number of new contacts established

Indicator 3.2: Number of new collaborations started

Indicator 3.3: Number of new community events on agrobiodiversity

Indicator 3.4: Number of new actors engaged in seed production

Indicator 3.5: Number of new projects on agrobiodiversity

Indicators 3.6: Increase in revenues on agrobiodiversity

Indicators 3.7: Quality of contacts and collaborations

Indicator 3.8: Rate of new contacts compared to vanishing contacts

Data collection methods:

- independent researcher collects data (interviews, questionnaires, online content analysis every 3 years)
- own statistics and reports by the hubs (annually)
- central agricultural statistics (KSH and other governmental statistics) (annually, if available)

Obstacles to indicator validity:

- validity of the indicators is heavily influenced by the quality of data and it can be an obstacle that the hubs do not have enough resources to prepare their own statistics and reports;
- financing of independent researchers and research programs is uncertain which threatens the implementation of monitoring activities;

- the ambiguity of terms (e.g. what does „active” mean?) can lead to uncertain and unreliable data;
- „the myth of numbers”: dominance of quantification over quality and meaning;
- faults of centrally collected statistics, especially those about the activities of small-scale market actors.

Desired change 4: Positive change in material (seed) stocks and flows + Increase in the genetic diversity of open pollinated vegetable varieties cultivated

Purpose: Interventions checked by the numbers reflecting the quality and quantity of seed material.

Indicator 4.1: Number of varieties managed by each hub and overall

Indicator 4.2: Number of varieties in vegetable gardens

Indicator 4.3: Number of gardeners saving their own seeds

Indicator 4.4: Number of seed exchanges organised

Indicator 4.5: Number of seed producers

Indicator 4.6: Quality of knowledge about cultivated varieties

Indicator 4.7: Number of registered varieties in the national variety catalogue

Data collection methods:

- independent researcher collects data (interviews, questionnaires, online content analysis every 3 years)
- own statistics and reports by the hubs (annually)
- central agricultural statistics (national variety register, KSH and other governmental statistics) (annually, if available).

Obstacles to indicator validity:

- validity of the indicators is heavily influenced by the quality of data and it can be an obstacle that the hubs do not have enough resources to prepare their own statistics and reports;
- financing of independent researchers and research programs is uncertain which threatens the implementation of monitoring activities;
- the ambiguity of terms (e.g. what does „active” mean?) can lead to uncertain and unreliable data;

- „the myth of numbers”: dominance of quantification over quality and meaning;
- faults of centrally collected statistics, especially those about the activities of small-scale market actors.

Desired change 5: Change in the seed system’s objective and paradigm towards caring

Purpose: Monitoring paradigm change

Indicator 5.1: Strengthened solidarity among actors

Indicator 5.2: Strengthened commitment and responsibility towards nonhuman actors

Indicator 5.3: Strengthened emotional attachment to seeds, varieties, agrobiodiversity

Indicator 5.4: Seeds are considered and managed as cultural heritage

Indicator 5.5: Agriculture is considered as a community of human and nonhumans in the long term

Indicator 5.6: Agricultural support based on the ecological and social qualities of production

Indicator 5.7: Small-scale agricultural production preferred over large-scale production

Indicator 5.8: Social status of agricultural activities

Data collection methods:

- media analysis every 3 years;
- attitude and value assessments; focus groups studies;
- policy and legal analysis.

Obstacles to indicator validity:

- difficulties and contradictions of data analysis
- sampling and response biases

5 Narrative of Broader Impacts

It is hard – or we would rather say: impossible – to predict how different actions and events influence each other, how and what gets individuals inspired, which novelties get accepted by society and which ones disappear in the long term. In this chapter, we decided to create a very diverse vision about what broader impacts can the intervention have, however, it's important to note that in order to live in a future envisioned like this, it is important to make steps towards it from several directions, not only from the side of agrobiodiversity.

The social image of agriculture is radically transformed. We no longer think of agriculture as a business sector among others. Farming is a unique practical area for nurturing the relationship between humans and nature, where humans and non-human beings live together as companions in a long-term balanced community. Nature (and some of its creatures, e.g. 'pests') is no longer an enemy to be conquered, to be harnessed, invaded and exploited by humans to meet their own needs. Agriculture is based on a relationship of solidarity, care and responsibility between humans and other beings – and it also shows in practice. It shows a high degree of respect for nature and the landscape (place) and does not elevate the needs of human beings above those of other beings. This creates a tradition of old/new agriculture in which the knowledge and status of farmers is socially valued and the care of seeds is considered to be a part of the conservation of cultural heritage.

The food system is transformed from the current market-oriented, growth-focused system, centralised and controlled by the central state, to a more flexible, landscape-based system, aiming at territorial food independence, organised primarily according to the principles of solidarity and social economy.

The power relations in society change. The autonomy of small-scale actors and their communities increases, while the power of large-scale actors is limited or even reduced.

In addition to the agriculture and food system, other sectors are also transformed. In the health sector, the healing role of nature, nutrition and the related ways of producing food are emerging as important factors (both as knowledge and in practice). Both education and popular culture are integrating the spirit of the new paradigm. Specifically, the value of agrobiodiversity and the practice of maintaining it are embedded at all levels of education. Art and other cultural sectors are tools and creative spaces that play a key role in the critical appropriation of the new paradigm. The research sector and the priorities and practices of science are also being transformed. Science cannot continue its ethos and practice of instrumentalising other beings in any field. It generates creative solutions and follows scientific paradigms where knowledge creation is not exploitative, but methodologies of learning and knowing (listening) with other beings prevail. Social work and community development disciplines are also increasingly taking into account non-human peers. In the financial sphere, constructs that do not treat humans and non-human beings and their communities at their intrinsic value are becoming impossible. In this process, the media act not as a servant of business and central government interests, but as a disseminator of the knowledge elements of the new paradigm (as a means of learning) and as a critical forum.

Public policy and policies also change. In particular, direct agricultural policies (e.g. EU CAP) will no longer support agricultural practices that destroy non-human beings and do not foster solidarity between people. With their transformation comes policy making and support practices that institutionalise the principles of sustainability and solidarity at the landscape level. Related policies are also changing to strongly support the institutionalisation of a new paradigm and system dynamics of agriculture. Among others, EU cultural heritage programmes will include agrobiodiversity among the heritage elements to be preserved. Related national policies are undergoing a similar transformation. Similarly, business practices affecting agriculture are changing.

The main obstacles to this transformation can be the following actors and factors: large business actors and their lobby groups, high-tech instrumentalising science and innovators, central government politicians and bureaucracies, habits and routines, the paradigm of growth.

The main drivers of this transformation could be the following actors and factors: NGOs and CSOs (non-governmental organisations), representatives of organisations that are at least partly organised on the basis of initiatives that address the needs of lower social classes, small-scale farmers, amateur gardeners, local authorities (especially if they look downwards rather than upwards), public gene banks, community gene banks, biodiversity specialists, social and low-tech innovators (who do not think on a huge scale), artists and cultural creatives.

Methodological Annex

The table below summarises the expert interviews conducted. We have chosen a rather common and rough classification of the main category of interviewees, which classifies the subjects according to the main sectors. We have tried to form the subcategories in such a way that they carry information relevant to the system under study and to "refine" the classification of the interviewees.

Main category	Subcategory	Number of interviews
Academic sector	Humanities	
	Engineering science	6
	Social sciences	1
	Natural sciences	
Government sector	Gene bank	
	Seed legislation	1
	Seed control	
	Other relevant sector	
NGO sector	Movement	6
	Subsistence farmer / hobby gardener	4
Media		1
Arts		3
Private sector	CSA farmer	4
	Food retailer	
	Catering industry	
	Seed distributor	
	Seed producer	1

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